

RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI

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ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqola ingliz badiiy adabiyotida ruhiy kasalliklarning berilishi va ularning tahlili yuzasidan fikr yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: roman, psixologik, xarakter, ijod, personaj, ijtimoiy-ma'naviy, ruhiy xastalik, epilepsiya, monomaniya

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz "yomon xastalik", "og'ir dard", "yomon kasallik" kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.

Kasallik, betoblik, xastalik — organizmga tashqi yoki ichki muhitning zararli omillari ta'sir etganda ro'y beradigan patologik jarayon. Kasallik haqidagi tushuncha tibbiyot tarixida o'zgarib bordi. Kasallikning paydo bo'lishida tashqi muhit omillari yetakchi rol o'ynaydi, chunki ular organizmga bevosita ta'sir etish bilan birga uning ichki xususiyatlarini ham o'zgartira oladi, bu o'zgarishlar nasldan-naslga o'tib, unda kasallikni yuzaga keltirishi mumkin¹.

Ruhiy kasallik atamasi ostida asab tizimlaridagi buzilishlar oqibatida paydo bo'luvchi, jamiyatda o'rnashib qolgan me'yorlardan keskin chiquvchi hatti-harakatlarga olib keluvchi kasallik tushuniladi.²

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kasallik>

² https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ruhiy_kasallik

Amerika adabiyotida ruhiy buzulishlar ko'pincha detektiv asarlarda, odatda, odam o'ldiruvchi ruhiy xasta (monyak) obrazi ko'p uchraydi. Jumladan amerikalik mashhur hikoyanavis adib Edgar Alan Poning "Berenis" hikoyasida monomaniya kasaliga giriftor bo'lgan Egeus (Egeus) ismli bemorning ayanchli hayoti tasvirlangan. Hikoya qahramoni Egeus o'qimishli yigit, amakivachchasi Berenis bilan katta, g'amgin qasrda o'sadi. U ruhiy buzulishdan, monomaniyadan (Bir g'oyaga kuchli bog'lanish bilan tavsiflangan ruhiy kasallik) aziyat chekadi. Bu epilepsiya bilan boshlangan va ko'pincha katalepsiya bilan tugaydigan g'alati kasalligi bor edi (o'liklarga o'xshash statsionar holatga tushadigan holat). Hikoyada bemor qiz quyidagicha tasvirlanadi:

As time passed, their illnesses were growing. Berenice increasingly physically transmuted, took on a pale, thin and extremely long hair, while those trances Egeus suffered more frequent and lasting. Egeus proposes marriage to Berenice, and two are still in a deplorable condition³.

Tarjimasi

Vaqt o'tishi bilan ularning kasalliklari kuchayib borardi. Berenis tobora jismonan o'zgarib bordi, rangpar, ingichka va juda uzun sochlarga ega bo'ldi. Egeusda esa kasalligi tufayli ruhiy bezovtaliklar, tutqanoq tobora kuchayib borardi, u Berenisga turmush qurishni taklif qiladi va ikkilasining ham sog'ligi ayanchli ahvolda edi.

U Berenisni go'zal tishlari uchun sevib qoladi va bu tishlarning o'zida bo'lishini xoxlaydi. Shu xayol uni kechayu kunduz bezovtalantiradi, faqat shu xayol bilan yashaydi. Ma'lumki, monomaniya kasalligi bir g'oya yoki mavzuga haddan ziyod ishtiyoq alomatlarini qamrab oladi, ko'rinadiki, ushbu hikoya hajman kichik bo'lsada, kasallikka xos alomatlar deyarli qamrab olingan va ochib berilgan, to bu asarni o'qimaguncha, uning matni bilan tanishmaguncha hikoyada kasallik alomatlari haqida so'z bormaydi, sezilmaydi, hikoya o'qilgach uning syujetida aynan nomi tilga olinayotgan kasallikning hikoya syujetida tugun ekani ravshanlashadi, shu tugun yechimi

³ <https://poestories.com/read/berenice>

insonlarni halokatga olib kelgani ochiladi, chunki har qanday xastalik insonlarni fojeaga, o'limga olib kelishi ayni haqiqat. Biroq kasallik har xil bo'ladi:

- 1) Tuzaladigan kasalliklar
- 2) tuzalmaydigan kasalliklar

Ruhiy kasalliklarning aksariyati tuzalmaydigan kasalliklar sirasiga kiradi, chunki tanadagi kasalliklarni odatda davolab bo'ladi, masalan, yara chaqa, ko'richak, ruhiy kasalliklar esa inson psixologiyasi (ko'zga ko'rinmaydigan holatlari), ruhi bilan bog'liq bo'lgani uchun davolash qiyin kechadi.

"Berenis" hikoyasida yigit ruhiy buzilish holatida, o'zini bilmagan holda, qizni uning go'zal tishlari o'ziniki bo'lishini xoxlagani uchun qiz dafn etilgach uni qabridan kavlab olib tishlarini sug'urib oladi. Bir so'z bilan aytganda, yigit o'zini kechayu kunduz bezovtalantirgan telbalarcha orzusini ro'yobga chiqarishga muvaffaq bo'ladi, ammo bu uzoqqa cho'zilmaydi, yigitning siri fosh bo'ladi, yigitning siri ochilishiga uning o'zini kasallarga xos tutishi sabab bo'ladi, ya'ni u qizning tishlarini sug'urib olishi uchun ishlatgan tibbiy asboblar qutisi qo'lidan tushib parchalanib ketadi hamda 32 ta oppoq tishlar har tomonga sochilib ketib siri fosh bo'ladi.

Edgar Allan Poning asarlari qorong'u mavzular, zo'ravonlik va psixologik jihatdan beqaror belgilar bilan mashhur. Edgar Alan Poning deyarli barcha hikoyalarida kasalliklar, ayniqsa ruhiyat bilan bog'liq kasalliklar, ruhiy buzilishlarni uchratish mumkin, bunga sabab esa yozuvchining murakkab hayot yo'li deya xulosa qilish mumkin, chunki uning tarjimai holini o'rganganimizda uning onasi va xotini sil kasalligidan vafot etgan bo'lsa, o'zi esa bir necha yillar davomida alkogolizmdan qutulolmagan, natijada umrining oxirida ko'chada behush holda topiladi va kasalxonaga yotqiziladi, bir necha kundan so'ng 40 yoshida sirli ravishda vafot etadi⁴. Jumladan

yoʻzuvchining "Chaqimchi yurak" va "Qora mushuk" uning eng mashhur ikkita asari boʻlib, ikkalasida ham aqli raso boʻlmagan hikoyachilar ishtirok etadi. "Chaqimchi yurak"da hikoyachi oʻzi yashayotgan cholni bu odamning koʻzlari bezovta qilgani uchun oʻldiradi. Xuddi shunday, "Qora mushuk"da ham hikoyachi oʻz mushukini oʻldirmoqchi boʻladi, lekin u hayvonni himoya qilmoqchi boʻlganida xotinini oʻldiradi. Majnunlik bu matnlardagi hikoyachilarning umumiy xususiyatidir. Bu dramatik istehzo, chunki oʻquvchilar hikoya qiluvchining aqldan ozgan va aqldan ozganligini bilishadi, lekin u buni bilmaydi.

It's true! Yes, I have been ill, very ill. But why do you say that I have lost control of my mind, why do you say that I am mad? Can you not see that I have full control of my mind? Is it not clear that I am not mad?.....I heard sounds from heaven, and I heard sounds from hell!⁵

Bu haqiqat! Ha, men kasal boʻldim, juda kasalman. Lekin nega aqlimni boshqara olmadim deysiz, nega aqldan ozganman deysiz? Men ongimni toʻliq nazorat qila olganimni koʻrmayapsizmi? Men jinni emasligim aniq emasmi?.....Jannatdan tovushlar eshitdim, doʻzaxdan tovushlar eshitdim!

Hikoya bosh qahramoni jannat va doʻzaxdagi gaplarni eshitayotgan boʻlsa ham, jinni emasligini oʻziga-oʻzi aytmoqda, bu esa uning aqliy sogʻlom emasligini isbotlaydi. "Chaqimchi yurak"da hikoyachi oʻzi yashayotgan cholni bu odamning koʻzlari bezovta qilgani uchun oʻldiradi. Xuddi shunday, "Qora mushuk"da ham hikoyachi oʻz mushukini oʻldirmoqchi boʻladi, lekin u

⁵ Edgar Allan Poe :storyteller, English Language Cultural division Educational and Cultural Affairs United States Information Agency ,Washington,D.C.20547,page 75.

hayvonni himoya qilmoqchi bo'lganida xotinini o'ldiradi. Majnunlik bu matnlardagi hikoyachilarning umumiy xususiyatidir.

Demak badiiy adabiyotda kasalliklar, xususan ruhiy xastaliklar yozuvchilar tomonidan mahorat bilan ifodalangan, ayniqsa kasalliklar, ularning simptomlari, bemor belgilari aniq ochib berilganligiga guvoh bo'ldik. Badiiy adabiyotda ruhiy xastaliklarni ifodalashning esa turli sabablari, yozuvchining ruhiy holati, oilaviy va ijtimoiy muhitning ham ta'sirini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

This article describes the image of imaginary diseases in the stories of Edgar Allan Poe and the reasons for writing about diseases. The allegory and symbolism by depicting the Red Death.⁶

The article is devoted to the analysis of the *The Magic Hat* book, written by popular Uzbek writer Khudoyberdi Tukhtaboyev, from the position of classification elements introduced by famous Russian philosopher, literary critic and scholar Mikhail Mikhailovich Bakhtin.⁷

The depiction of natural landscapes given in works of art is one of the factors that demonstrate the creative artistic skill.⁸

В современной методике так же, как и много лет назад, актуальной и нерешенной до сих пор остается проблема поиска и выбора наиболее эффективных и рациональных

⁶ Akhmedovna, B. M., & Shakhnoza, B. (2022). The Image of Disease in Edgar Allan Poe's "The Masque of the Red Death". *Pindus Journal of Culture, Literature, and ELT*, 2(1), 19-22.

⁷ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). ANALYSIS OF TRANSFORMATION MOTIFS IN THE MAGIC HAT BOOK BY KHUDOYBERDI TUKHTABOYEV, THROUGH THE PRISM OF MIKHAIL BAKHTIN'S THEORIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 405-408.

⁸ Kabilova, F., & Tokhirovna, T. K. English Translation of Abdullah Qadiri's Novel "Days Gone by" and Its Reflection Skills. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(10), 304-306.

методов преподавания иностранных языков, соответствующих современным условиям обучения и отвечающих требованиям стандартов современного образования.⁹

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory.¹⁰

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹¹

This lesson plan format moves from teachers to centered student. In order to keep this standard lesson plan format from becoming monotonous, it is seminal to memorize that there are a number of variations that can be applied within the various segments of the lesson plan format.¹²

This article deals with the analysis of pastiche in literature, particularly in “The Lightning Thief” by American author Rick Riordan. The research identifies pastiche as a term, which is applied to a literary work that is a broad mixture of things-such as themes, concepts, and characters-imitated from different literary works.¹³

⁹ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

¹⁰ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹¹ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹² Nodirovna, N. N., & Temirovna, P. M. (2022). Principles of designing lesson plans for teaching ESL or EFL. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 5, 10-12.

¹³ Khabibullaeva, R. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PASTICHE IN THE NOVEL “THE LIGHTNING THIEF” BY RICK RIORDAN. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 958-961.

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.¹⁴

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day.¹⁵

В этой статье дается краткий обзор антропонимов, их функций статуса, который они получают от этих, и их специфики.¹⁶

The article is about the development of the Soviet era of Uzbek educational dictionary. The educational dictionaries created during this period served mainly to teach Russian in national schools.¹⁷

This article deals with the description of synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language published in different periods, the systematic description of the similarities and differences between the explanations of synonyms in the publications.¹⁸

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the right of citizens to vote and to be elected, the foundations of the national electoral system, the basis of which are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and ratification by Uzbekistan, constituting the principles of democracy, including independence,

¹⁴ Куницька, І. (2014). Роман-біографія як жанровий різновид модерністського роману (С. Моем Місяць і мідяки"). *Сучасні літературознавчі студії*, (11), 342-348.

¹⁵ NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

¹⁶ Орипова, К. (2022). ОНОМАСТИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОСТИ ВО ФРАНЦУЗСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz)*, 8(8). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4712

¹⁷ Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). HISTORY OF CREATING FIRST BILINGUAL AND REGULATORY EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 4(1), 147-181.

¹⁸ Rustamovna, M. G. (2020). Presenting synonyms in the explanatory dictionaries of the Uzbek language. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 117-120.

legitimacy, transparency and fairness, enshrined and recognized in other international legal instruments.¹⁹

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.²⁰

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